

Research

An ethnographic Study on Beggars at Hyderabad city of Sindh-Pakistan

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Accepted: 29 October, 2020; Online: 19 November, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4281616>

Abstract: The worst issue which Pakistan is facing today is ‘Street Begging’. The Nation is suffering from the crucial situations of Poverty which has forced hundreds of people to commit suicide, forced women to sell-out their Children and forced young’s to leave their Homes and start begging. According to latest survey 74% of our people living under poverty line earning less than 4000/Rs per month which is very difficult for a person to live in so little amount, even one cannot imagine to survive. But a Street Beggar is earning more than a Person doing hard slog. Street begging disturbs Public life because usually this beggar on the Roads, Streets & Bazaar’s chasing people for petite amount. To gain more attention and sympathizes they generally irritate public with their disgraceful mannerism. They emotionally black mail the genders by telling their gloomy stories & by showing their disabilities. Begging is supposed to be an easy source of earning Money. This is the reason that most of the physically fit young persons are usually seen begging on the Streets. This profession now has become an Industry (Mafia) where young men, Women & Children are mostly trained, recruit and relocated. These Beggars and specifically Children come from the Cities of Kohat, Rahim Yaar Khan, Multan, & Rawalpindi. According to a survey Beggar Children earn 200 or 250 rupees per day and handover entire money to the Mafia (Which works for this profession) and that Mafia keep a big chunk of earning and leave minimum amount with to these Children to take home. This Mafia is taking more benefits of the Street Begging.

Keywords: ethnographic, Beggars, Socio-economic condition.

Introduction

It is an interesting area for anthropologists to study the current human organizations and its problem. Begging is also going to be a structured business involving white-collar people from top to the disable children in the bottom. Geographical areas are distributed in the beggars and no one allow each other to begging in their territory. Especially, urban poverty, migration, crime, poor governance, poor urban planning and policies are the major causes of begging. Urbanization is rapidly growing in Hyderabad; geographically the city is expanding day by day. The families belonging from the rural Sindh province of Pakistan frequently migrate to migrate to cities of Sindh province of Pakistan due to the lack of livelihood resources in rural areas especially after the massive floods and bad condition of agriculture due the shortage of water in Indus River since last decade. People prefer to migrate to Hyderabad city of Pakistan and Karachi, city of Pakistan however due law and order situation of Karachi city; many communities wish to settle in Hyderabad city. It observed that in 2010 floods that thousands of families migrated to Hyderabad city after the destruction of their homes and resources in rural Sindh, province of Pakistan. Though the large number of migrated population settled back to their native villages but yet many families especially to very poor background preferred to stay in Hyderabad. Though there are comparatively having more bread winning opportunities and availability of labor options, but the city cannot offer the work opportunity for all. There are very small numbers of industrial areas as compared to other big cities of Pakistan. It was also observed in the flood relief efforts in 2010 floods that there was a large numbers of camps of migrated peoples from rural Sindh and different NGOs philanthropists and the settlers of Hyderabad continuously supported these migrated people still months; instead of taking some efforts to help those peoples to work and labor opportunities this may also have boosted the trend of dependency and begging. This research will highlighted the major cultural aspects of the baggers i.e. the economic activities, customs, food, residential, dress pattern, of baggers in Hyderabad city province of Pakistan. Trend of begging is increasing day by day mostly in children, profession of begging especially in Pakistan is supposed to be related with specific professional casts. Begging is basically a social problem which reflects the less number of work opportunity, poor socio-economic system and poor governance. It has been observed since last few decades that due to the increasing poverty and inflation trends this profession is spending in its non-traditional professional casts, we observe lot of children, young, old male and female and

disable people increasing on traffic signals, markets, and populated areas day by day. poor socio-economic system, inadequate work opportunities and bad governance result in several social problems in the society, the begging is the one those problems that is on hike in Hyderabad city province of Pakistan. Indeed, Begging has become a profession. It is carried on as an art. Every one of us has seen various kinds of beggars; some are blind, lame or crippled, and so take to begging. Some people, who have lost their homes, become beggar. Child and orphan beggars also are very common. Their methods of begging are equally varied and strange. The causes of begging are many. First of all, some people are physically incapable of doing any work. The only way of getting food open to them is begging, such beggars easily win the sympathy of others. They deserve it also. But the number of such Leprous, Blind, or otherwise invalid beggars is not very great as compared to other kind of beggars.

Objectives of the study

- To explore and documents of the social problem of begging in Hyderabad city province of Pakistan.
- To explore and documents of the causes of begging in Hyderabad city province of Pakistan.
- To explore the socio-economic condition of beggars in Hyderabad city province of Pakistan.

Literature review

This second chapter presents the relevant review of literature on the topic of beggars and issue of begging. For this purpose, I have attempted to present different source materials on the issue of beggars to understand the social problem of begging. As mentioned in the first chapter, the present study is an ethnographic study. Therefore, first I would like to present in this chapter about what is ethnography which is used by anthropologists to study human society. The word “ethnography” is combination of two words, i.e. Ethno plus graph, where the word ethno means people or culture and graphy or graph is ‘to write about’. Writing about particular culture or group of people by using ethnographic research methods, is known as ethnography. In this research study, views of different scholars, anthropologists and academics have been incorporated to strengthening the findings during the field work. The history of Anthropology reveals that initially it was based on the Ethnographic account of different cultures, which were exotic and intrigued the European. According to the Karan Raj, “A Subset of cultural anthropology concerned with the study of contemporary cultures through first hand observation”(Raj, Karan. Dictionary of Anthropology, p.177)An ethnographer is an anthropologist who attempts in his professional work to record and describe the culturally significant behavior of particular society. An ethnography requires a long period of intimate study and residence in a small, well defined community, knowledge of spoken language and the employment of a wide range of observational techniques including prolonged face to face contact with members of the local group, direct participation and use of key informants during the field survey and data collection specifically. As C.P Kottak stated, “Ethnography thus emerged as research strategy in societies with greater cultural uniformity and less social differences”. (Kottak, 2002: p.34)The strategy of ethnography is like that of natural history to approach general knowledge by building up a large series of case studies, which can inductively be compared and contrasted with one another. The basic style of ethnography developed a stress on field study. Ethnographic research consist of case studies of one social unit, usually a historical chieftom, etc. The cumulative efforts of ethnographers to go beyond the uncritical narrative and rambling presentation of assumed cultural details have focused on determining what constitutes a valid cultural description, on developing a theory, that permits evaluation of alternatives descriptions, and formulating methods that may be most effective in deriving general statements from recorded observations. According to Fellix M. Keesing (1958)“Ethnography is

the description of custom that is a local way of life".(Felix 1958: p. 35)The central place of ethnography and its major tenets were articulated in Britain by Bronislaw Malinowski and in United States of America was Franz Boas. Malinowski learned the language of the Torbrianders and explored their everyday life. He observed and recorded quarrel, work, errands, jokes, family scenes, festivals, stories, Voyage, and other events. Franz Boas is known as founder of anthropology in United States. He advocates the study of specific cultures in their particular historical contexts, as approach called "historical particularism". In his critique and comparative method, he suggests that to understand general processes, anthropologist should understand the historical processes of individual societies and compare them."Ethnography is a descriptive account of social life and culture in a particular social system based on detailed observation of what people actually do"(Johnson, 2006: p.101)"This term (ethnography) is used with two distinct senses: that of ethnographic research (fieldwork) and that of an ethnographic monograph (ethnographic writing). As a category of anthropological research, ethnography is characterized by the first hand study of a small community or ethnic group. Such studies combine to varying degree descriptive and analytical elements, the central characteristics of conventional ethnographic are that they focus on one specific culture or society and consider the theoretical or comparative generalizations from the stand point of ethnographic example." (Seymour, 1986: p.98)Ethnographic studies usually are holistic, founded on the idea that humans are best understood in the fullest possible context, including: the place where they live, the improvements they have made to that place, how they make a living and providing food, housing, energy and water for themselves, what their marriage customs are, what language(s) they speak and so on, in short about their culture Whereas culture is the addition to the Nature. It means that, whatever men adopted for making their living possible historically that was becoming part of its culture or in other words that became their way of life. While the term culture is most common and important in the field of anthropology and in fact the anthropology is some time known as the 'cultural anthropology'. Most of anthropologists use the term culture as the synonym of a society. Whereas the term society refers to a group in which many or all people live and think in same way.

Edward B. Taylor is known as the father of the discipline of anthropology. He defines culture as:"Culture is that complex whole, which includes knowledge, belief, arts, morals, laws, custom and any other capabilities and habit acquire by man as a member of society."(Kottak, 2002:

p.268)For a long time, community studies and ethnography has been the most prominent ways for anthropology and sociology, to understand the social reality. It was assumed that local communities were microcosms of human culture. The term Community has a range of meanings in anthropology and sociology. In its broadest sense it may refer to;“Any group of persons united by a community of interest such as a professional group, residential unit, like village or town, a sector within such a unit or a club or voluntary association may all be referred to as communities”(McMillan Dictionary, 1986: p.46)

Data analysis

Interviews

This chapter focused on causes of begging, socio-economic condition of beggars and this chapter also studies the kinds of beggars and the tricks they use to get sympathy of people in Hyderabad city. This is clear that begging is increasing with poverty. The history of begging is silent but according to the religious point of views the history of begging dates back to many centuries ago by the name of God and peoples started to give them charity, sadaqa, and zakat etc. Some examples are given above in chapter 2 literature review. Beggars are begging in all over the world but the large ratio of beggars are founded in India and Pakistan. Because these countries are most poor, dense populate and religious in believes some beggars are really needy like handy capped, some of them just professionals and begging is there source of income using their tricks. Children who are orphan are reluctantly begged for their livelihood. Now a day begging is being a profession which is being adopted by even white collar people. They just wanted the sympathy of the people and use their emotions to beg.

Types of Beggars in in city Hyderabad Sindh Pakistan

Qalandarifaqeer

These beggars their spiritual connection with the shrine of HazratLaalShehbazQalandar

The beggar seen in the above picture is from Mehar. He has 7 family members all are begging in different cities for their livelihood needs. He has 4 sons and 3 daughters, his wife died during the birth of his last child. He travels to different areas of the province for begging. At the time of interview he was in Hyderabad since three days. He begs from morning to the late night and take lunch and dinner from the hotel by suppliant. At first he was terrified of giving the answers of questions but when taken his confidence he felt comfortable for the conversation. This beggar is roaming in different cities for begging since last 30 years. He doesn't know about his parents due to the death of them when he was a child. **Causes;** for his begging was just to survive his children and his life because he doesn't have any skill for occupation. His daily collection of begging was nearly 300 to 400Rs. except money he receives the clothes and different things from his begging specially in the Ramazan and during the Eid he gets zakat and new clothes by begging. He doesn't have any property except only a single Hutt. He receives more money on Friday as compare to other days.He always uses the religious customs for supporting his begging in the name of Mola Ali A.S and PanjtanPaak. Also he uses the name of Saint QalandarLaalShehbaz. His dressing and appearance shows the relation with the Qalandari Fakir

and he used to call him by this way. He sleeps at the dargah in the night Like in Hyderabad Kadam Gaah Mola Ali (as) and in Sehwan the Shrine of LaalShehbazQalandar and SamanSarkaar.

Jogi beggar and snake charmer;

Manthar (kanfar)
Age 30 years
Begging area
Hyderabad
(His daily begging is
above than 500Rs.)
Begging is his
kindred profession;
he has no other
cause of begging
without poverty.
And he is also a
snake charmer

Manthar is 25 years old, he is basically from Tharparkar and from past 20 years he is settled at Bhit Shah. He married when he was 17 years old, and he has 4 children. He gets up early in the morning and ready to go for begging. He wear in the field the traditional dress of jogi's like (gerru) long shirt (kamees) and loose trouser (salwar) and a (gerru) turban on the head a stick in the hand and begging shopper which is madden by quilt, and he also take a snake in box and flute for dancing the snake and entertaining the people with that.

He begs in different areas of the city and visits his home after 10 to 15 days for caring of his family and gives them support. He contributes financially to his wife and children. He lives in the colony of the Jugis which migrated from Thar to Bhit Shah. He told that begging is the

inheritance job for him. He is here in Hyderabad since last 2 days Except begging he catches the snake and offer jewel for the fortune of the people for which he don't fix the price but just depend upon the person who pay for its worth. He gets daily begging more than 500Rs and except money he also begs floor and wheat.

Catching Snake: He told me that to catch the snake they use to give sworn of Badshah Pir to the snake for which they recite the Mantara to stop and catch it easily. Some days when snake bites they put the snake manka to suck the venom of snake. He told that there are many kinds of snakes they catch but there is only one snake which they don't catch is LUNDO snake which is the power full from all and don't even obey with any kind of Mantara of the Pir.

Power of Stone Jewels: Manthar told that the stone jewels are affected by the names and the zodiac symbols of the people. They know how to use those jewels for any particular use such as to pass in the exams or getting married or being healthy and solve the problems of life which they bring from the Lahoot (Noorani Noor). He has many kinds of the stones like Aqeeq, Ferozo, Zarqoon, Yaqoot, Marjan etc.

Jogi beggars;(who call themselves the baggers of shrine Hazrat Shah Abdul Latif Bhitai)

Piyaro chohan;
jogi beggar, Age
36 years, Begging
area near honda
palace hyd. He
started begging
from childhood.
Cause; Begging is
his kindred
profession. His
daily begging
income is 400 to
500 Rs.

Beggar seen in the above picture is basically from Umerkot and from past 10 years he is settled at Bhit Shah. He has 8 family members some of them are begging in different towns. He is the only guardian of 4 daughters, 2 sons, one wife and a mother. He travels different areas of the province for the begging. Begging is his kinfolk's profession; he started begging from childhood. He told me that he learned begging from his forefathers. Piyarochohan is 36 years old. He is a sufi (faqeer) and his dressing and begging tricks are different from others. He was not begging only money but he also begs wheat flour and other things for eat from shops, he begs to the houses dor to dor and streets. He was not only begging but he was also selling stone rings (jewels).His daily collection of begging was nearly 400 to 500Rs and Friday is the golden day for him. He collects more charity on Friday, except money he receives the used clothes and different things from his begging. He has no any other source of income without begging, he start begging from early morning to 5:00/6:00 AM at different spots and then he go back to home, and he is taking different routes for begging. He has no any property without a hut. **Cause of begging**

Because of poverty and children he begs for the survival. Also he gets more money as compare to the daily labor worker. It is observed by them that they have the MIDAS HAND where ever they spread people never refuse them (faqeergisonikisti aa jadywendikhalinaendi)

Female beggar;

*Rahat- Female
Beggar. Age 50 years,
Area of begging
railway station
Hyderabad.*

*Daily beggary 300 to
400RS*

*She started begging
from past 8 years.*

The beggar in the above picture is from Hala, She has seven children, 4 daughters and 3 sons. Her husband was dead; who was drum beater for the ceremonies. After his death she started begging since last 8 years. She usually begs in the Hyderabad from morning to the late night.

She begs in the name of Allah and shows her poverty for begging. She earns more than 5 hundreds.

Cause of begging: She doesn't have any guardian for her children so due to poverty and unskilled she uses to beg at different spots for fulfill her livelihood needs.

Professional beggar

Gulzarsiyal is 52 years old lives in Jamshoro and he is married has 3 sons who are also begging at different spots and he also has 4 daughters. Eight family members depend on him he is the only guardian of them. He told that they lived as a family of six brothers with his father, when he was a cobbler. After the death of his father all brothers divided by the family reasons and he shifted to the Jamshoro. Then he started begging because he doesn't have any skills for professions but the money which he got from his father's property he opened a tuck shop for his son. His other 2 sons use to beg like him. He usually begs in the city of Sewhan, Bhitshah, Hyderabad and Jamshoro. He goes to his house at the night or sometime he sleep at the different shrines of the saints in the city.

Causes of begging: He is begging because of poverty, he begs in the name of Allah. He uses to wear tearful clothes to take emotional attainment of the people and get more charity on that. He daily collects 4 to 500 Rs by begging. He gave me the interview and went quickly because he said he wanted to go for his habit otherwise he will not survive.

Begging Tricks: He uses to wear the dress like malang and use to call him as a follower of the Qalandar Laal Shahbaz. People believe in the majestic powers of the laal qalandar that's why they don't feel hesitate to give charity for their own wishes.

Mannu Shaikh: poor migrant (disable beggar)

*Mannu: is a
disable
beggar*

*Age 30 years
old*

*Living in a
hut of
nomadic
community
and he was
my key
informant*

He is 30 years old. Live in the huts at bhitai nagar. He is handicapped by legs. He broke his legs when he was a child riding on the camel and feel down. He is living Hyderabad since last 15 years. He married 10 years ago and has 2 children. His begging spot is fixed at the entrance gate of Gulistan e Sajjad where he begs from the passing cars. Police was disturbing him for not begging at this spot but he got help from a person who is belonged to his village and now he don't botheredby police anymore. Everyone knows him specially the shopkeepers and the workers at C.N.G station. At the time of interview I observed a person who buy him 5kg beg of flour. He just begs 4 to 5 hours only in a day. And whatever he gets he took all that to his house. He uses the wheel chair to travel from his house to this spot which is nearly 300m in the distance. He doesn't roam in the streets like other beggars and not insist people to forcefully give him money. He just raises his hand for begging without chanting high voices.

Gahi lahoti faqeer (he is known themselves the beggar from lahoot noorani noor)

Gahi lahooti;
Age -38 Years
Basically from
new saeedabad,
His daily begging
is more than
700Rs.
Begging area civil
hospital and
tower markit
Hyderabad.

Beggar seen in the above picture is basically from village Raess Nazir ahmed, New saeedabad. After that they shifted to Bhit Shah. All other family members are there, he came for begging to Hyderabad, because he think that people are more wealthy and rich so he get more charity. He started begging since last 5years before that he worked in the fields with whole family. After the death of his father, every one become on its own, his other brothers are drivers in different areas. He has only a mud house in village, the land lord is making troubles for their family and wanted to sweep their houses but they managed to save it. He is begging in Hyderabad since last 2 days, he married and has 2 children. His in-laws are living in jamshoro, he use to stay there at night. Mostly he gets charity from shops of market and from attendance of the patients from civil hospital. He gets more than 700Rs in a day from begging, and poverty is the cause of his begging.

Disable beggar;

Dilshadhalepoyo;

Age 30 years

Begging area hyd

*He becomes
beggar because he
is disable he has
polio, begging is
his only source of
income.*

Beggar seen in the above picture is Dilshad Halepoto from Bhit Shah. He is 30 years old. 10 years ago he got married and he have 3 daughters. From past 15 years he continue begging in Hyderabad, according to his belief Hyderabad is most populated city and here's people are richer. He is begging on the moving cart traveling round the city and especially at the public spots like parks and schools. He believes that people are more helpful to him as he is victim of polio he could not walk or stand so he cannot work anywhere to earn. He is getting food from hotels in begging and some time he pay bill. He sleeps outside of the hotels and masques and he visit his family at village after 5 to 6 days in a month.

Cause of Begging: He is just begging from his handicapped condition and for his survival of the family. So for this he got the moving cart on which he is traveling here and there easily.

Female Beggar

Name: Radhabai

Residence: Near Bhitai Nagar, nomadic community.

Place of begging: near bakramandi Cause of begging:

She is begging just because her husband is a drug edict and don't go for work that's why she have to earn for her family and children. She cried during the interview and told her story that she is help less otherwise the begging is very cheap to her family system where she belongs. She is from the Thakur cast so it was so much difficulty she faces in her community as well.

Tricks of Begging: She used to carry her daughter for taking child sympathy by the people and need urgent attention for her child. She never let any people to go without giving the money. She chases them to some place for convincing people to understand her needs and feelings for her child.

Field Data& Findings

Poor migrants, poverty and Begging

The field data and findings of beggars who are involved in begging. The special focus of this chapter is to present the data and findings of the group of poor migrants who are involved in begging. There are two groups settled in this area. One of them is SHAIKH and other is BHEEL. There are 35 homes of Shaikh and 20 houses are belonging to Bheel community. They came from different parts of the Sindh, Shaikh community migrated from District Badin and Bheel came from Thatta and Tharparkar. There are different reasons for their migration, like lack of resources in their villages, tribal disputes between them, some of them just wanted to adopt the facilities of the city to change their lifestyle and also some just mean to beg only. The causes of begging is poverty, illiteracy, over population, forces them to beg, some of them are really needy and some are professional beggars, begging is in kinsfolk's profession. The causes of their migration Just by begging from all over the city, and collect paper garbage to exchange them with some money for their survival. Their living style is very simple they live in the groups, in the tent made homes; which are not good to protect them in the swerve weather like raining or winter cold breeze. The conditions of their homes are really worst; the area on which they made their house is full of waste water and not clean they are just living without any kind of facilities. The most important problem is about their shelter which is temporary and second thing is about their security which they feel uncomfortable at all so they wanted the help always by facing illness or the disease.

They just call themselves as gypsy so they don't care about their living standards or style.

They are settled in Hyderabad from past 6 years near bypass, opposite bhitai nangar colony, Qasimabad. The community comprises on 55 households spread over 2 acres, which are divided in two groups one are bheels (Hindus) and second are sheikhs (Muslims). There were 35 houses of sheikhs and 20 houses of Bheels. Total population 360 people (male 190 and female 170) which are shown below in the table.

Population of community

S no	House hold	Male	Female	Total	Male percentage	Female percentage
1	55	190	170	360	52.7	47.2

Occupation

They are living through various occupations, daily wage labor, gatamerin, and begging. Mostly they are begging specially children and women. All old women and children are beg young women do the domestic work, care for the children, cook food, clean the house and also help their male in the field.

Occupation	No of male	No of female	Total	Percentage
Begging	75	55	130	36.11%
Garbage collect0r	60	00	60	16.66%
Fruit seller	10	5	15	4.16%
Total	150	60	210	58.33%

Conclusion;

This study focus on socio-economic condition of beggars causes of begging as a social problem and the typical lifestyle and residence pattern of beggars in Hyderabad Sindh. The Sindhi local culture has more impact on the dress, marriage and settlement pattern of this community. In the dress pattern and marriage pattern this nomadic community became closer to other Sindhi. Women used to have chadar (a piece of cloth used to cover the head) for pardah (veil) when they go outside from their home or when they face any person of other caste. The marriage pattern of Beggars (nomad community) is determined by patrilineal descent which is traced through the male line. Normally the marriages among them are arranged. Cousin marriages (with the daughter and son of father's brothers and father's sister and the son or daughter of mother's brother or mother's sister) are common. Early marriages are quite common in community. They are living with joint family system which is more dominated by fathers. Some of them also have nuclear family system. In joint family system they share the same Chula (stove) and common purse. The joint income results in the preference for joint family. The sheikh members of the community also celebrate the rituals of “rites de passage”. The ritual of birth includes Azan in the ear of baby, Chhathi in which name for baby is selected, Jhand in which hair of baby are being shaved first time after birth. The ceremony of circumcision is also observed in this community. Marriages rituals include ritual of Tareekh (fixation of date of marriage), ritual of Wanwah, ritual of Nikkah, etc. Death ritual includes gusul, coffin, namaz-i- janaza, ritual of taddo etc. Some of them were the snake charmer, beggars but nowadays they have left the technique of snake charming and started to collect paper or plastic garbage, children’s are all usually begging from different spots like near roads, streets, locale hotels. The old community members (Male and female) of community prefer begging. Among community, women participate in economic activities. Old women beg whole the day from sunrise to sunset and bring handsome amount of rupees. The money earned is usually spent in daily household expenditures. Only women are involved in cooking, cleaning of house and child rearing tasks. Men have more social interaction with other communities than women. The husband remains the real decision maker but women have got the freedom to run the daily expenditures of household because her active involvement in the economic activities.

References

1. Al-Halwani Dr Ali, How Islam Solves the Problem of Begging,
2. AzharMobeen, Child victims of Pakistan's 'begging mafia', June 02, 2013)
3. Begging is haram! (<http://alilmiyah.tumblr.com/post/15076638577/begging-is-haram>, Retrieved on 9, Sep, 2013)
4. Begging, Sahihmuslim, Taj series. (Sahih Muslim, vol. 2, p. 498, no. 2271 and Sunan Abu Dawud, vol. 2, p. 430, no. 1636)
5. (Baily, 1952: p.174) "For a researcher rapport establishment is one of the most essential tasks after the entering into the field. But it can be most difficult and consuming task in the field work."
6. (Fellix 1958: p.35) "Ethnography is the description of custom that is a local way of life".
7. (fellix 1958; p. 35) "Ethnography is the description of custom that is a locale way of life"
8. (<http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/magazine-22729351>, Retrieved on 9, Sep, 2013)
9. Gilanimasroor AFP, Begging Becomes a Business in Pakistan, April, 26, 2013 (http://www.google.com/hostednews/afp/article/ALeqM5g_3LB55n5G67GiETvs-LLXdQJrxA?docId=CNG.e5b5da19972901a32dc71775a79c694f.a1, Retrieved on 9, Sep, 2013)
10. HaroonFizza, Street Begging- Feb, 10, 2011, pakistan today, sep, 28, 2013. (<http://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2011/02/street-begging/?printType=article>.) Retrieved on 9,
11. <http://www.onislam.net/english/shariah/shariah-and-humanity/shariah-and-life/461975-begging-avarice-and-contentment-labor-work.html?Life=>, Retrieved on 9, Sep, 2013
12. Is Begging in Islam Allowed?, My Islam. (<http://myislam1.weebly.com/is-begging-allowed-in-islam.html>, Retrieved on 9, Sep, 2013)
13. (John collier, 1967; p.92) "Photography is a must for all anthropological field work"
14. (Johnson, 2006; p101) "Ethnography is a descriptive account of social life and culture in A particular social system based on detailed observation of what People actually do"
15. (Kottak, 2002: p.268) "Culture is that complex whole, which includes knowledge, belief, arts, morals, laws, custom and any other capabilities and habit acquire by man as a member of society."
16. (Kottak, 2002; p.34) "Ethnography thus emerged as research strategy in societies with greater cultural uniformity and less social differences"

17. Khan Humayon Ahmed, Beg, Beggar and Begging, Society and Culture (<http://www.hamariweb.com/articles/article.aspx?id=9691>, Retrieved on 9, Sep, 2013
18. Khan sibga, Beggars in Pakistan, oct, 2005, css forum (<http://www.cssforum.com.pk/off-topic-section/humorous-inspirational-general-stuff/1251-beggars-pakistan.html>
19. (Pelto&pelto 1978; p.42) “It is often useful to employ more than one measure or made of observation in the study of particular cultural institutions”.
20. (Pelto&Pelto: 1978: p.79) “Key informant interviewing is used to best advantages when it is closely integrated with participant observations”.
21. (Raj, Karan. Dictionary of anthropology, p.177) “A subset of cultural anthropology concerned with the study of Contemporary Cultures through first hand observation”
22. (Russell Bernard, 1994: p.86) "Good informants are people, who talk easily, understand the information you need, and who glad to give you or get it for you".
23. (Russell, 1994: p.136) “Participant observation involves getting to people and making them feels comfortable enough with your presence so that you cannot serve and record information about the words lives”.(Sahih Al-Bukhari, vol.2, p.319, no.549)
24. (Webster, 1985: p.64) “A sample is a finite part of a statistical population whose properties are studied to gain information about the whole”
25. (Yin, 1984: p.14) “The case study contributes uniquely to our knowledge, individual, organizational, social, political phenomena; in brief, case study allows an investigation to retain the holistic and the meaningful characteristics of real live events.”

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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